

ABSTRACT

HISTORY OF TRIBAL - BANJARA GYPSE
TRADITIONAL LIFE & EDUCATION

by

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TRIBAL HISTORY & LIFE OF TRIBALS

Introduction

the history Tribals and the current situation of the Banjara Gypsies in Andhra Pradesh. It begins with the origins of the people and describes the present political, social, and cultural context. It ends with the religious and economic contexts of the Banjara Gypsies located at Gandiganumala village in the Guntur district.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AD	Anno Domini
BC	Before Christ
DBS	Discovery Bible Study
DFID	Department for International Development
KM	Kilometer (0.621371 Miles)
LFA	Logical Framework Approach
LFM	Logical Framework Matrix
MLA	Member of the Legislative Assembly
MP	Member of Parliament
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NIV	New International Version
OBC	Other Backward Class
SDA	Seventh-day Adventist
ST	Scheduled Tribe (Castes)

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POLITICAL, SOCIAL, CULTURAL, AND RELIGIOUS CONTEXTS OF THE BANJARA GYPSIES

Introduction

This chapter deals with the history and the current situation of the Banjara Gypsies in Andhra Pradesh. It begins with the origins of the people and describes the present political, social, and cultural context. It ends with the religious and economic contexts of the Banjara Gypsies located at Gandiganumala village in the Guntur district.

Origins of the Banjara Gypsies

Gypsies are named differently in different territories. The origin of these people in India dates back 2,300 years. They live in parts of Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Bihar, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Odisha, and West Bengal, sometimes wandering from one place to another and living out a unique culture. The identity of the so-called "Gypsies," "Banjara Lambadi," or "Lambadi Gypsies" and their origin is controversial, and several theories exist. However, one theory states that they descended from European Roma gypsies, who migrated across the mountains of Afghanistan and settled in Rajasthan's deserts and other regions of India (Indian Mirror, 2023). According to Donald Kenrick, in the early accounts of Gypsies in Europe, some references are made to Indian origins. The history of Indian origins is

not told by Banjara Gypsies and has been replaced by the idea that they are from Egypt. However, investigations into the origins of the Romani language showed that it came from northern India and had been brought to Europe by the Gypsies (2010, 123). "The linguistic and cultural affinities of Banjaras with those of Northern India suggest that their homeland

was possibly Rajputana, particularly Marwar in Northern India. They migrated south as merchandise carriers along with the Moghal armies” (Pratap 1968, 3).

According to another account, the Banjaras claim descent from Mota and Mola, two brothers who tended Sri Krishna’s cows. The descendants of Mota include the modern Marwaris, Mathura Banjaras, and Labhanas. The story goes that a prince rewarded Molawas for performing gymnastics with three little boys and his wife Radha’s beauty. His descendants are called Charan Banjaras (Hassan 1920, 17).

According to the statements of D. R. Pratap, other authors mention that migration to south India, especially to parts of Telangana, parts of Karnataka, and parts of Andhra Pradesh, took place during the Aurungzeb period. One theorist has written that,

R.V. Russel, in his book *Tribes and Castes of Central Provinces of India*, writes that Banjaras migrated to Deccan along with the forces of Aurungzeb. Mr. Cumberledge has mentioned that Banjaras first came to the Deccan with the Asaf Khan in the campaign, which closed with the annexation by Emperor Shah Jahan of Ahmed Nagar and Berar about 1630 A.D. (1968, 4)

There are different theories about Banjara Gypsies, their existence, and migrations, but most likely, the Banjara Gypsies migrated from Northern India based on the available history. Along with the history, the Gypsies’ lifestyle and culture give evidence that they migrated from North India.

Etymology of the Word Banjara

Syed Siraj ul Hassan writes, “Banjara is supposed to be derived from the Persian *Berinj Arind*, which means ‘dealer in rice’. Some derive it from the Sanskrit Banij—a merchant. The Banjaras have other names, such as Lamani, derived from the Sanskrit Lavana—salt; Wanjari, from Vana—a forest; and Lambadi, from Lamban—length, which is probably a reference to the long line or train in which their bullocks move” (1920, 16).

J. J. Roy Burman argues for another possible meaning, “The term ‘Banjara’ also indicates that they were forest dwellers. The Arab rulers also referred to them derogatorily as forest dwellers” (2010, 15). The Joshua Project states, “The Banjara’s name is derived

from the word *bajika*, which means trade or business, and from *banji*, meaning peddlers pack." Because of the work and travel these Lambadi Gypsies do, they received this name.

Roy Burman states, "According to Motiraj Rathod, the Lamans migrated to India from Afghanistan. Laman was popular long before the name 'Banjara' became known. The Banjaras considered the Lamans as their Gurus and did not oppose the name Laman being suffixed by the people. Motiraj Rathod feels that the name Banjara evolved only from the time of the Mughals" (2010, 15). Laman Banjaras probably derive their name from the local language as they carry and sell salt or *lavan* from place to place. It is also said that their business practice in their language and Sanskrit *vanijya* led to them being called Banjaras (2010, 15).

Burman adds, "The Gor usually refer to themselves as Banjaras and outsiders as Kor, but this usage does not extend outside their community. A related usage is Gor Mati or Gormati, meaning *own people*" (2010, 13-14).

Beyond studying the etymology of the words Lambadi, Banjara, or Gypsies, it is essential to understand their sub-tribes as they relate to these people wherever they live. According to the Sri OSVD Prasad, the Director of Tribes and Tribal Areas of Andhra Pradesh, "The tribe of Lambadi's/Gypsies is divided into five phratries, they are 1. Bhukya (Rathod), 2. Vadthiya (Jadhav), 3. Chowhan, 4. Pamar, and 5. Banoth (Ade). In their dialect, these Phratries are further divided into several patrilineal kin groups called Pada or Jath (Clan). At the same time, Bhukya Phratry consists of 27 clans, adthiya 52 clans, Chowhan 6 clans, Pamar 12 clans, and Banoth 13 clans" (2004, 31). It is possible that the many different identifying names can lead to confusion, which could hinder the ability to engage this group of people meaningfully.

Demographic Statistics

The population of the Lambadi Gypsies in Andhra Pradesh is around three to four million (*Indian Mirror* 2023). The population of Banjara stands at seven million, according to the Joshua Project **in India**. In Gandiganumala, the local place where this research is taking place, as per the population census of 2011, 923 families reside in the village of

Gandiganumala. The total population of Gandiganumala is 3,850, out of which 1,934 are males and 1,916 are females. The population of children aged 0-6 years in Gandiganumala village is 638 or 17%. There are 308 male children and 330 female children between 0-6 years old (*Gandiganumala Village Population 2021*).

Influence of Subsequent Groups

The Banjara community has left a significant impact on India's history. Their migratory patterns have taken them across India, North to South, and to different parts of the world. This movement has significantly influenced their identity and cultural practices. Overall, however, their influence is less because "they are also physically and emotionally harassed by the upper-class people. They are downtrodden people in the country who are educationally, socially, economically, and politically disadvantaged" (Chandra et al. 2017, 567). Therefore, the influence of these people groups on others is limited. They do, however, influence each other within their nomadic communities.

Description of the Place

The Banjara Gypsies are predominantly found in the Indian states of Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Karnataka. Gandiganumala, the focus of this research is located in Andhra Pradesh, and serves as a focal point for understanding the Banjara community's geographical and historical context. Understanding the geographical and historical nuances of Banjara Gypsies, particularly in Gandiganumala, provides valuable insights into how these people live and what is important to them.

Geographic Description of Location

Gandiganumala is a village in Bollapalle Mandal in Guntur District of Andhra Pradesh State in India. The meaning of the name of the village is "a mountain pass" (Crussiah et al. 1959, 1). It is located 107 KM west of the district headquarters in Guntur, 13 KM from Bollapalli, and 195 KM from Hyderabad, the united capital of Andhra Pradesh and

Telangana. The languages spoken by these people are Telugu and Urdu. Agriculture serves as the main occupation in this village. This village is still waiting for industrial development. Education, drinking water, roads, and electricity are still primary needs for this village.

History of Location

The Banjara Gypsies originally came from the state of Rajasthan in India and divided themselves into groups that went to different states around India. While specific historical events or figures associated with Gandiganumala are not detailed in history books, villages like this often have a deep-rooted history that can be traced back through local folklore, traditions, and administrative records.

According to local folklore, people believe Banjara Gypsies migrated to Gandiganumala before the 1950s, when there were forty families.

Other Groups Present in the Location

Additional groups of people located near the Gandiganumala village are *Gangls* and *Idiga*. The *Gandla* community, numbering approximately 1,900 individuals, is part of the O.B.C. Hindu people. Their primary language is Telugu, and their religion is Hinduism (People Group 2024a).

The *Idiga* community is another group present near the location. They are part of the O.B.C. Hindu people cluster, and their primary language is Telugu. Various alternate names are associated with this community, including Gowda, Goundala, Kalali, Gamalla, Settibalija, Vadugan, Gavara, Halepaik, Ediga, Iliga, Billava, Devaru, and Divaramakkalu. There are approximately 81,000 individuals residing near the location. Their primary religion is Hinduism (People Group "Idiga of India" 2024b).

Banjara Gypsies in the Location

Banjara Gypsies are considered a Scheduled Tribe (S.T.) by the government of India. Scheduled Castes/Scheduled Tribes and backward Castes (OBC) refer to specific groups of people recognized by the government of India for affirmative action and social justice. In this location, 62.6% of Banjara Gypsies reside, and the rest of the 37.4% belongs to other people groups. The literacy rate of these people is 30.9%, and most of them have relocated to get jobs in nearby towns and cities. Thus, Gandiganumala village has a lower literacy rate than 60.6% of Guntur district. 59.6% of workers have permanent jobs, while 30.4% are involved in marginal activities (Gandiganumala Village Population 2021).

Political Context

Concerning the Lambadi Gypsies politics, “The Indian Constitution has the provision of reservation in politics for Scheduled Castes/Scheduled Tribes and backward Castes, but the political representation of the Banjara community at the national level is not satisfactory” (Bhimdeo Rathod 2017). Beyond that, the political participation of women is meager. The status of women in the Banjara community varies from *tanda* to *tanda* (local settlements). “Their role in the development of the region or economy has been greatly administered in the last few decades.” Unfortunately, the Banjara community has no strong women giving political leadership. This lack of representation makes it difficult for them to access social, economic, and political rights (Rathod 2017).

Vaditya Venkatesh, in his handbook, quotes from Booker (2018)

The dominant castes like Reddys, Kammas, and Velamas dominate the government and politics in Telugu states. For instance, from the inception of Andhra Pradesh to 2018, there have been 888 ministerial posts. Out of these post-Reddys occupied 248 (28%) posts, Kammas 116 (13%), Velamas 45 posts (5%), Kapus 62 (7%), SCs 111 (12.5%) and S.T.s 22 (2.48%). Reddys occupied the chief minister post 14 times, Kammas 7 times, Velamas 3 times, and S.C., Brahman, and Vysyas each once. (2021, 175)

The following quote sums up the challenges for the Banjara gypsies politically. “In the present context, their vulnerability worsens due to unresolved issues like displacement,

land alienation, indebtedness, shifting cultivation, and deprivation of forest rights. The development activities undertaken by the state so far in India have displaced Adivasis in a large number. In most cases, these displaced people have still not been rehabilitated properly" (Vaditya 2021, 167).

Local Politics

According to OSVD Prasad, Banjara Gypsies use a traditional council for each *tanda* to resolve disputes for economic and social issues. This council consists of one headman (*nayak*), one advisor (*karbari*), and one messenger (*dappan*). All the council offices are hereditary. They call the traditional council *naiker ghar* (2004, 32). Gandiganumala falls under the [assembly constituency](#), where Bolla Brahma Naidu is the present M. L. A., and the *lok sabha* or parliamentary constituency, Lavu Sri Krishna Devarayalu is the M. P.

Influence on Banjara Gypsies

In local politics, the Banjara community has representatives who advocate for their rights and interests. These representatives are part of village *panchayats* (regional governing bodies) or other community-led organizations. Like other marginalized communities, the Banjaras encounter challenges, including poverty, limited educational opportunities, and restricted access to resources. Local politics are crucial in addressing these challenges by advocating for better infrastructure, healthcare, education, and livelihood opportunities.

Lavu Sri Krishna Devarayalu, a prominent political figure in the Palnadu region, has announced his determination to continue his work for the development and well-being of the people. In a recent meeting attended by over 200 people from the Sugali and Lambadi communities in Bollapally Mandal, Gandiganumala village, Devarayalu reiterated his commitment to completing various projects crucial for the region (The Hans India 2024).

Social Context of Banjara Gypsies

The Banjaras have distinct socio-cultural traditions, including their Thanda settlement, attire, language, festivals, gods, rituals, and manners apart from public life. Banjaras have a different culture, independent public life, and distinctive customs of subsistence from those around them. These characteristics are displayed in their dietary habits, festivals, rituals, worship, likes and dislikes, dances, songs, languages, and clothes.

Marriage

The Banjara Gypsies have unique customs when it comes to marriage. "The status of Banjara tribal women is markedly better than that in the Hindu caste society. Women play an important role in the domestic economy of tribal societies. They are usually allowed to move freely and have the right to choose their marriage partners or at least have a large say in this; it is always, at the very least, a family affair" (Lal 2009, 290).

When understanding the marriages between the clan and with other people groups from the local society, Babu Chinna Jamia Nayaka states,

[The] Banjara tribe was divided into four clans, Rathod, Pamhar, Chauhan, and Vaditya, with several sub-clans within them. Each clan was exogamous and could not marry within the same sub-clan as they were considered brother and sister. A man can marry his sister's daughter, mother's brother's daughter. Banjara man cannot marry a maternal uncle's or auntie's daughter; such is considered incest. (n.d., 8)

In the Banjara community, early marriage for girls is practiced. The "tribe usually as soon as the girl reaches puberty she was given in marriage. For girls, the age will be 14-16 years; for boys, the marriage age was 17-20 years" (Nayaka n.d., 8). The girls are often open to this arranged marriage from the moment they reach adolescence, and when a proposal is made, their parents would typically act in opposition before the girl's father seeks the guidance of his **nayak** and the village elders.

Regarding intermarriage with other people, "A non-Banjara girl will be taken in marriage, but a Banjara girl will not be given to a non-Banjara boy" (Nayaka n.d., 8).

When considering marriage among Banjara Gypsies, one must first understand that there are four types of marriage: (1) marriage by service, (2) marriage by exchange, (3) marriage by elopement, and (4) widow marriage. (8, 9) Most of the marriages in the Banjara Gypsies fall under these categories. According to Prasad (2004),

each phratry is an exogamous unit, and one has to marry outside his phratry clan is a patrilineal kin group . . . but inter-group marriages are strictly prohibited, . . . Upon marriage, a girl loses her parents' clan name and adopts her husband's clan name. . . marriage by negotiations is the only accepted way of performing marriages and sometimes marriage by service is also practiced. The married women wear ivory bangles or imitate them above their elbows, referred to as "Balìa." (32)

The *Indian Mirror* states that,

Banjaras welcome the groom's family by offering betel leaves and nuts. On the day of marriage, the boy and girl exchange seven round balls made of rice, ghee, and sugar, which is the unique thing about a Banjara wedding. Then, the couples hold hands and do seven rounds of grain pounding with pestles. A square silver ornament bottu is tied around the neck of the bride. The groom's family is given a sound feast. A band of material tied around the waist strengthens a skirt or trousers. (2023)

Polygamy was permitted in the past, but monogamy is the norm now. However, for reasons such as a childless wife, sick wife, birth of only girl children, widow of a close relative, and so on, the man is permitted to marry a second or third wife, keeping all the wives with him. However, in recent times, this system has decreased in Banjara because of the lack of availability of women and increased awareness of health issues.

Sorcery, Magic, and Charms

Banjara Gypsies have a rich tradition of magic and sorcery that is deeply embedded in their culture. Banjara Gypsies invoked their ancestors for fruitful results in their journey, robbery, work or family, and fortune. They also used magic, charms, and sorcery for good and bad purposes (Nayaka n.d., 10).

The sorcery, magic, and use of charms among Banjara Gypsies reveal much about their lifestyles and beliefs. Magic, the use of amulets and talismans, and divination are common practices of these people.

The Banjara Gypsies have a strong magical heritage, with practices that include love spells, charms for protection, and rituals for recovering stolen property. They believe in the power of amulets and talismans, carrying items like coins or stones that are thought to be imbued with magical properties. Divination and fortune telling are also significant parts of Banjara Gypsies culture, often associated with their women, who have been engaged in these practices since ancient times. These beliefs and practices have been passed down through generations and continue to be an important part of Banjara Gypsies and their identity.

Treatment of Women

Women in the Banjara Gypsy community are treated with low respect in the society when compared with the other women in Indian society. The rights of women are low, and they have to follow their husbands in all areas. Banjara Gypsy women are not supposed to let their hair down or comb it when they are in the presence of males. Additionally, it is expected that a lady should walk behind a man instead of in front of him. They need to respect men in all aspects of their lives.

Banjara Gypsies are also known for their frank communication style, but they also uphold specific moral standards. Chastity is highly valued in their culture, and in the past, women associated with prostitution were sometimes buried alive. Even today, it is not acceptable for single women to travel alone into cities. If they must go, they often cover their hands and feet when seated with strangers (Joshua Project 2023, 4).

Banjara women are not strictly subordinated to men and are not entirely inaccessible. Women are allowed to divorce and remarry, and if unjustly deserted, they can be given half the portion of their husband's property. Women are also involved in agriculture, animal husbandry, firewood collection, and cattle breeding, and they contribute to the family's income by "embroidery, known as Lambani or Banjara

embroidery, [which] is rich in colors, patterns, and embellishments like mirrors and beads, and . . . [is] a significant aspect of their cultural heritage” (Team UCN 2023).

Women can engage in social and religious activities, but only men are given the authority to speak and conduct ritual ceremonies. The *thanda nasab* system is male-dominated, preventing women from leading the *thanda*. The property and succession in the family transfer to the eldest son. Due to the influence of outside society, modern education, and contact with the wider world, women’s roles and places have changed, and in some ways women’s lives have improved (Nayaka n.d., 10).

Education among the Banjara

The Banjaras were primarily non-literate, as they lived a nomadic life that did not allow them to learn in formal educational settings. According to Nayaka, in his paper, he quotes other authors such as Colonel Mackenzie, who claims that “A Banjara who can read and write is unknown. However, their ability to memorize are marvelous and very retentive” (Russell 2007, 171). Still, due to the impact of modern education, K. S. Singh says, they prioritize education for boys but show less support for girls’ education. Their children often drop out of educational institutions due to poverty, disinterest, and various social reasons (Nayaka n.d., 12).

There were reasons why the Banjara did not emphasize education. First, they were nomads, often moving from place to place. Second, the whole family was involved in trade and cattle breeding. Third, education was only given to a section of society, whereas the Banjara were marginalized. Fourth, people discriminated against them, so Banjara struggled to mix with wider society (Nayaka n.d., 13).

Because of their nomadic existence, the Banjaras have not traditionally kept written documents. Since there is no written script for the Banjara dialect, songs, ritual music, folklore, stories, myths, proverbs, and phrases serve as the main means of preserving and disseminating the Banjara people’s history and customs.

Unfortunately, the literacy rate among the Banjara Gypsies in Andhra Pradesh is not explicitly mentioned in the available data. However, it is essential to recognize that the overall literacy rate in the state remains below the national average.

Economics of the Banjara

During the Aurangzeb's reign (1658-1707), the Banjara Gypsies played a vital role in the economy through their marketing practices.

Prasad states that the Banjara Gypsies are skilled cattle breeders who primarily earn their livelihood by selling milk and milk products. In modern times, they have settled on land and have become adept agriculturists. Families without land migrate to towns and cities, seeking employment by driving and pulling auto-rickshaws. Additionally, they work as laborers, earning daily wages in building, road work, and other infrastructure projects (2004, 32).

The *Indian Mirror* states,

The occupation of Banjaras is in the gathering of forest products and agriculture. These tribes are experts in traditional hand embroidery with mirror works. The artwork of Banjara Tribes is in good demand in the market in various states of India. Articles of silver, brass, gold, cowries, ivory, animal bones, and even plastic decorate the wardrobes of fashionable urbanities. (2023)

Prior to the entry of the British into India, the Banjara community's economy flourished through exchanges utilizing bullock carts; however, as the mode of transport developed, it hindered the financial life of the Banjara community. Vaditya states that the Banjara people used to make a living by using their bullocks to pack goods, and they still remember the names of some of the army generals who employed their forebears. When peace and the railways came and did away with these callings, they fell back for a time upon crime as a livelihood, but they have now mostly taken to agriculture and grazing. As their business diminished, they resorted to dacoities and cattle stealing. Even today, most Banjara live in severe poverty, with very few holding white-collar jobs (Vaditya 2017).

Cultural Context

Banjara individuals have asocial lives that separate them from others. Their dialect, nourishment, dress and adornments, craftsmanship, body inking, and ceremonies shape the social world of Banjara individuals. The deluge of present-day life and the increasing contact with the non-Banjara world has had an impact on the Banjara social life (Nayaka n.d., 10).

Food

The *India Mirror* states that the primary food of the Banjara people is Bati, which is Roti. Daliya is a dish cooked using many cereals (wheat and jawar). Banjara people like non-vegetarian food, such as Saloi (made from goat blood and other parts of the goat), and they prefer eating spicy food (2023, 5).

Other traditional cuisines of the Banjara people include Ghuggari, consisting of boiled cowpea, red gram, and land gram, and rice is occasionally consumed. Patali baati is a special dish made from high-quality wheat, bajra, or ragi, often served with chicken curry or boiled green leaves. The Banjara community abstains from consuming beef. Additionally, Banjara dogs are renowned for their ability to hunt wild animals (Nayaka n.d., 11).

Dress

The *India Mirror* highlights that Banjaras are well known for their colorful attire, with Banjara women's dress being one of the most elaborate and vibrant among the various tribal communities in India. They wear *ghaghra* and *choli* (a blouse), with the *ghaghra* skirt featuring red, black, and white cotton and embroidery with mirrored glass. Additionally, they wear silver anklets. The materials used in crafting a Banjara wardrobe include silver, brass, gold, cowries, ivory, animal bone, and even plastic, reflecting the tribe's rich cultural heritage and aesthetic sensibility (2023, 3-4).

Art and Dance

The Banjara community, a nomadic tribe in India, has a rich cultural heritage that includes vibrant art and dance forms. One aspect of dance called the “Lambadi Dance” originated from the Banjara community in Andhra Pradesh. This special folk dance is based on centuries-old traditions and heritage. It is characterized by energetic movements and rhythmic stomping, often accompanied by traditional instruments like the Thali and Dholak (Tourism 2022).

Banjara art is encompassed in various forms, such as embroidery, tattooing, and painting. Embroidery in Banjara art is highly prized. It features colorful and unique designs, often seen on clothing and textiles. Tattooing is another significant aspect of Banjara’s identity, which will be covered in more depth in the next section. The paintings of the Lambadi Banjara often feature beautiful paintings of nature and the culture of people. These artistic expressions are not just aesthetic; they are intrinsic to the Banjara identity and survival, reflecting their rich cultural heritage and daily life stories.

“Both men and women sang folk songs. Precession, bronze plates, and cymbals were the musical instruments. Both men and women dance to the tune of the drum. Fire dance and Chari are the traditional dance forms of banjara people” (Dhanavath 2020, 42). Art and dance are special features of this people group. There “are traditional musicians and bards . . . [the] Lambadi’s called ‘Dappans’ who depend mainly on the gifts presented by Lambadi on various occasions. There are three divisions among Dappans: 1. Bhat, 2. Dhandi and, 3. Dhalia. Bhats and Dhadis sing songs about family history by playing musical instruments called *Jange* and *Kinjri* during marriage ceremonies” (Prasad 2004, 32).

In addition to traditional music, Lambadi Gypsies have special music for their festivals and worship services. While the musicians play, other gypsies dance and participate in the festival. They feel it is the way of receiving the blessings of their gods and goddesses, “Various dance forms are performed during the festival” (India Mirror 2023, 4).

Tattooing

In the Banjara community, tattoos are somewhat frequent. Similar to other Banjara costumes, tattoos convey the wearer's individuality, sense of self, and kinship. Some believe that tattoos can stave off illness and bad luck. "Like their decoration on costume with mirrors, tattoos are also decorative for beauty and protection from ill health or recognition. This tattooing form[s] a significant aspect of the Banjara people" (Dhanavath 2020, 41).

Religious Context

Lambadi Gypsies adopt the local religion and practices of the location in order to receive blessings and to be protected from the elements that harm their community. This section describes the festivals, ancestor worship, spirits and demons, rituals of death, and the availability of Bible translations to the Lambadi Gypsies.

Festivals

The religious life of Banjara focuses on worshipping nature, the sun, fire, water, and the earth. The festivals, gods, rituals, beliefs, and ceremonies are peculiar to Banjara people. Banjara follows some aspects of Hinduism but has also developed its practices.

Many Banjaras celebrate major Hindu festivals such as Dusshera, Diwali, Ugadi, Holi, and Ganesh Chaturthi, and they recently started celebrating the New Year. During Holi, women perform the *kolata* dance and collect alms. *Teej* is a festival for young men and women, and *Bhog* is a significant ceremony for a newborn's first haircut and dedication. Cowries worn by Banjara women symbolize their devotion to the Goddess Lakshmi (Nayaka n.d., 15).

The Banjara community is well-known for its preference for non-vegetarian food. They perform animal sacrifices during different events such as weddings, festivals, rituals, journeys, and celebrations. In addition, they also perform sacrifices during times of illness,

death, and pilgrimages. The act of offering sacrifices to their gods and ancestors is an integral part of Banjara's religious and cultural practices (Nayaka n.d. 15).

Ancestor Worship

"The Lambadi also worship and pay reverence to the benevolent Gods such as Vishnu, Rama, Venkateswara, and Seva Bhaya. Meraima is beloved for protecting their females and children and preserving the fertility of their lands and females. At the same time, Seva Bhaya and Seetala are regarded as the protectors of the cattle" (Prasad 2004, 32). Banjaras originally worshipped aspects of nature and held strong beliefs in ancestor worship. Men perform 'Pitru puja' during Diwali and Holi by offering 'Dhabkar' to the fire, while both genders participate in common evening prayers led by the head of the family on the east side of their settlement (Thanda), facing west (Nayaka n.d., 15).

Spirits/Demons

Since the Banjara community blends elements of Hinduism with their indigenous traditions, they "believe that the world is protected by many spirits—benign and malign" (Prasad 2004, 32). The Banjara people believe in magic and spirits, seeking the Bhagat for positive outcomes and the dukun for harmful intentions. They also believe that the spirits of those who die from unnatural causes become demons that trouble the living (Nayaka n.d., 15-16). As a result, they worship the spirits of the dead.

Rituals of Death

The India Mirror reports that Banjara,

believe that death is a universal phenomenon and that all living things have to die one day, and they are aware of the fact. The death of old persons is good because their old are transformed into new ones, or they get salvation. In their community, premature death is not as good as it occurs due to accidents, murder, suicide, burning, etc. The unnatural deaths are the main reasons that the souls of the people become malevolent spirits. (2023, 4)

“The dead are cremated in separate cremation grounds” (Prasad 2004, 32) since Banjara people are not usually interested in placing their dead along with other people groups or other castes.

In Banjara tradition, the deceased are buried with their heads facing north and legs south, a practice still followed by the Gor people. In some areas, married individuals are cremated, while unmarried people are buried. The death announcement is made by a “Samgo” or “Saat Wego.” The community then gathers at the bereaved family’s home to show support, sharing water from a single pot. On the third day, relatives collect donations and sacrifice a goat to provide for the grieving family.

As part of their custom, the ritual is conducted outside the Thanda under a tree where relatives and the Naik prepare a rice cake mixed with jaggery and ghee known as “Churmo.” After offering water and Churmo to the deceased, the remainder is shared among those present. They believe that Churmo must be consumed on-site and cannot be taken home. This ritual is unique to their community and is not practiced by any other group to honor the deceased (Nayaka n.d., 15-16).

SUMMARY:

This research provided the details of the Banjara Gypsies who migrated from northern India and settled in Southern India. Knowing the origins, political, social, cultural, and religious contexts of the Banjara Gypsies or Lambadi Gypsies and to help the world understand situations of tribals . In addition, understanding their cultural practices will help in communicating the Gospel and developing digital cost effective classes and other nearby schools.